

Synthesis, characterization, thermal, electrical conductivity and biological studies of Schiff base metal complexes

N. J. Suryawanshi^a, G. B. Pethe, S. G. Bhadange^b and A. S. Aswar*

Department of Chemistry, Sant Gadge Baba Amravati University, Amravati-444 602, Maharashtra, India

E-mail : aswar2341@rediffmail.com

^aDepartment of Industrial Chemistry, Arts, Science and Commerce College, Chikhaldara-444 807, Maharashtra, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Shri Shivaji College, Akola-444 001, Maharashtra, India

Manuscript received online 25 April 2012, revised 28 August 2012, accepted 22 November 2012

Abstract : The coordination complexes of Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Ti^{III}, Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Zr^{IV} and UO₂^{VI} with new Schiff base derived from 3-acetyl-6-methyl-2H-pyran-2,4(3H)-dione (dehydroacetic acid) and thiocarbohydrazide have been synthesized. These complexes have been characterized on the basis of elemental analysis, IR and electronic spectra, magnetic moment and thermogravimetric analysis. The complexes are colored and stable in air. The ligand acts as dibasic tetradentate nature and forms 1 : 1 (metal : ligand) complexes with the metal ion. The thermal behavior of metal complexes show that the hydrated complexes lose molecules of hydration first; followed by decomposition of ligand molecules in the subsequent steps. The solid-state electrical conductivity of ligand and its complexes have been measured over a wide range of temperature in their compressed pellet form and the complexes are found to be of semiconducting in nature. The ligand and its complexes have also been tested for their antimicrobial behavior against various microorganisms and all complexes show a good activity.

Keywords : Hydrazone Schiff base complexes, IR spectra, DC conductivity, TGA, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

A large number of Schiff bases and their metal complexes have been studied because of their interesting and important properties such as their ability to reversibly bind oxygen and their use in catalyses for oxygenation and oxidation reactions of organic compounds redox systems in biological processes, aldol reactions, degradation of dyes through decomposition of hydrogen peroxide and reagents in textile industries¹⁻⁵. Dehydroacetic acid is an important biologically active compound. Schiff bases derived from dehydroacetic acid also have been found to be biologically active as well as excellent chelating agents^{6,7}. The chemistry of thiocarbohydrazide H₂N-NH-CS-NH-NH₂ compounds and their derivatives has been well reviewed⁸. The hydrazine group of this compound shows normal reactivity towards carbonyl compounds and is expected to yield Schiff bases which contain N, S and O donor atoms and therefore the derivatives can function as suitable ligands for transition metals. These Schiff bases

interact with metals in various possible ways. Variety of metal complexes of such ligands derived from thiocarbohydrazides have been synthesized and their stereochemistry has been reported⁹. The present study deals with the preparation of new Schiff base derived from 3-acetyl-6-methyl-2H-pyran-2,4(3H)-dione (dehydroacetic acid) and thiocarbohydrazide (H₂L) and its chelates with Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Ti^{III}, Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Zr^{IV} and UO₂^{VI}. The solid complexes have been synthesized and studied by elemental analyses, spectroscopic characterization, thermal and biological studies. The dc electrical conductivity of ligand and its complexes at different temperatures is investigated.

Results and discussion

Condensation of dehydroacetic acid with thiocarbohydrazide readily gives rise to the corresponding imine which is easily identified by IR and ¹H NMR spectra. The physical and analytical data of the ligand and its

Table 1. Analytical data of ligand and the complexes

Sl. no.	Proposed composition of the complexes	Formula weight	Colour	Time of reflux (h)	Elemental analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)			
					M	C	H	N
1.	H ₂ L	406.41	Yellow	5	-	51.04 (50.24)	4.89 (4.46)	14.10 (13.79)
2.	[MnL·2H ₂ O]	495.36	Dark olive	6	11.37 (11.09)	41.89 (41.22)	4.51 (4.07)	12.01 (11.31)
3.	[CoL·2H ₂ O]	499.36	Terre-verte	7.5	11.10 (11.80)	40.09 (40.89)	4.19 (4.04)	11.81 (11.22)
4.	[NiL·2H ₂ O]	499.12	Dark red gray	6.5	11.90 (11.76)	40.14 (40.91)	4.19 (4.04)	11.72 (11.23)
5.	[CuL]	467.94	Burnt umber	4	13.96 (13.58)	44.12 (43.63)	3.68 (3.45)	12.17 (11.97)
6.	[TiL·Cl·H ₂ O]	505.72	Yellow gold	4	9.03 (9.46)	40.45 (40.87)	3.12 (3.59)	11.90 (11.08)
7.	[CrL·Cl·H ₂ O]	509.86	Sea mist	9	10.07 (10.20)	40.19 (40.05)	3.12 (3.56)	11.13 (10.99)
8.	[FeL·Cl·H ₂ O]	511.86	Olive gray	5	10.37 (10.20)	40.19 (40.05)	3.59 (3.56)	10.37 (10.99)
9.	[Zr(OH) ₂ ·L]	529.63	Khaki	6	17.03 (17.22)	30.26 (30.27)	3.68 (3.43)	10.61 (10.58)
10.	[UO ₂ ·L]	674.42	Brown yellow	5	35.09 (35.29)	30.26 (30.27)	2.47 (2.89)	8.88 (8.31)

complexes are summarized in Table 1. The isolated solid complexes are stable in air and are insoluble in water and common organic solvents but soluble in DMF and DMSO. The elemental analyses show 1 : 1 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry for all the complexes.

Infrared spectra :

In order to give conclusive idea about the structure of the metal complexes, the main IR bands were compared with those of the free ligand. The IR spectrum of the free

ligand shows a medium band at 2874 cm⁻¹ due to the intramolecularly hydrogen bonded hydroxyl group¹⁰. The absence of this band in the spectra of metal complexes indicates the breaking of the hydrogen bond and coordination of oxygen atom to the metal after deprotonation. The phenolic C–O stretching vibrations appeared at 1297 cm⁻¹ shifted towards higher frequencies by 28–12 cm⁻¹ in the complexes suggesting that the -OH group takes part in the complexation via deprotonation¹¹. Ligand shows

M =	Mn ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Co ^{II}	Ti ^{III}	Cr ^{III}	Fe ^{III}	Zr ^{IV}	UO ₂ ^{VI}
X =	H ₂ O	-	H ₂ O	H ₂ O	H ₂ O	H ₂ O	H ₂ O	-OH	=O
Y =	H ₂ O	-	H ₂ O	H ₂ O	-Cl	-Cl	-Cl	-OH	=O

Scheme of the complexes

a strong band at 1657 cm^{-1} due to azomethine $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ group. On complexation the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ band shifted toward lower wave number *ca.* $\sim 50\text{--}15\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating the coordination of the azomethine nitrogen to the metal ion¹². This is also supported by positive shift of the $\nu(\text{N}-\text{N})$ band at 947 cm^{-1} of free ligand by $35\text{--}10\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in case of the complexes. In the zirconium(IV) complex, the absence of a band at $850\text{--}950\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\text{Zr}=\text{O}$) favours the formation of $\text{Zr}(\text{OH})_2$ and not $\text{Zr}=\text{O}$. The appearance of a new band at 1140 cm^{-1} has been assigned to the δ $\text{Zr}-\text{OH}$. The dioxouranium complex exhibits IR band at 902 cm^{-1} due to $\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{O}=\text{U}=\text{O})$ vibrations indicating the existence of linear $\text{O}=\text{U}=\text{O}$ moiety in the complex. The band corresponding to the stretching vibration of the $\text{C}=\text{S}$ group appears at 1092 cm^{-1} in the ligand and do not undergo considerable change in complexes, ruling out the possibility of bonding through this group. The conclusive evidence of the bonding is also shown by the appearance of new bands in the spectra of the complexes at $563\text{--}507\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $482\text{--}431\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assigned to $\text{M}-\text{O}$ and

$\text{M}-\text{N}$ vibrations respectively which are not observed in the spectrum of the free ligand¹³. The spectra of Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Ti^{III} , Cr^{III} and Fe^{III} exhibited broad bands in the $3160\text{--}3600\text{ cm}^{-1}$, region that are attributed to OH of water coordinated molecules. Furthermore the bands observed at 837 cm^{-1} , are assigned to coordinated water molecule. The presence of coordinated water is also established and supported by TGA. Hence from the IR data, it can be inferred that the ligand function as dibasic tetradentate ONNO molecule.

Magnetic moment and electronic spectra :

The electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded in the solid state in the $350\text{--}1700\text{ nm}$ range and reported in Table 2. The electronic spectrum of Mn^{II} complex shows three weak absorption bands at 588, 420 and 375 nm which are assigned to the transitions ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}({}^4G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}({}^4G)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g({}^4G)$, respectively, suggesting an octahedral geometry¹⁴. These electronic transitions and observed 5.91 B.M. magnetic moment value

Table 2. Electrical conductivity, magnetic properties and electronic spectral data of ligand and its complexes

Sl. no.	Compd.	Electrical conductivity σ ($\Omega^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$) at 373 K	Activation energy (eV)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Electronic spectra	
					Absorption band (nm)	Assignment
1.	H_2L	4.86×10^{-12}	-	-	-	-
2.	$[\text{MnL}\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	4.46×10^{-11}	0.048	5.91	588 420 375	${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}({}^4G)$ ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}({}^4G)$ ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g({}^4G)$
3.	$[\text{CoL}\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	4.67×10^{-9}	0.049	4.80	988 619 413	${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$
4.	$[\text{NiL}\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	2.63×10^{-6}	0.054	3.18	942 580 402	${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$ ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$
5.	$[\text{CuL}]$	1.05×10^{-11}	0.067	1.84	659 581 493	${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ CT
6.	$[\text{TiL}\cdot \text{Cl}\cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$	1.68×10^{-10}	0.054	1.79	544	${}^2T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$
7.	$[\text{CrL}\cdot \text{Cl}\cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$	4.12×10^{-11}	0.046	3.92	555 412 246	${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ ${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$ ${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$
8.	$[\text{FeL}\cdot \text{Cl}\cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$	6.85×10^{-8}	0.054	5.88	739 560 437	${}^6A_{1g}(S) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$ ${}^6A_{1g}(S) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$ ${}^6A_{1g}(S) \rightarrow {}^4E_g, {}^4A_{1g}(G)$
9.	$[\text{Zr}(\text{OH})_2\cdot \text{L}]$	6.36×10^{-9}	0.052	Diamagnetic	-	-
10.	$[\text{UO}_2\cdot \text{L}]$	1.56×10^{-10}	0.027	Diamagnetic	-	-

suggests octahedral geometry around Mn^{II} ion. The Co^{II} complex exhibits three bands at 988, 619 and 413 nm corresponding to ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transitions, respectively, for an octahedral geometry¹⁵. The reflectance spectral parameters for Co^{II} are found to be $Dq = 649 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $B' = 667 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\beta = 0.68$, $\nu_2/\nu_1 = 1.59$ and $\beta^\circ = 32$. The Racah parameter (B) value obtained for the Co^{II} complex is lower than that of free ion value, which indicates orbital overlap and delocalization of d-orbital, lower the value of B , greater will be orbital overlap. The β values for the Co^{II} complex is less than one also indicates considerable amount of covalent character in metal-ligand bond. The magnetic moment calculated for Co^{II} complex is 4.80 B.M. indicating high-spin character. The electronic spectrum of Ni^{II} complex exhibits three bands at 942, 580 and 402 nm, which may be due to the transitions ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$, respectively, suggesting octahedral geometry around Ni^{II} ¹⁶. The crystal field parameters for Ni^{II} complex are found to be $Dq = 1061.5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $B' = 684.73 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\beta = 0.66$, $\nu_2/\nu_1 = 1.62$ and $\beta^\circ = 33.46$. The reduction of Racah parameter (B) value from the free ion on chelation indicates the appreciable amount of covalent character in the metal-ligand bond. The magnetic moment of the Ni^{II} complex is found to be 3.18 B.M. This is within range (2.80–3.30 B.M.) found for paramagnetic Ni^{II} complexes with an octahedral geometry. The electronic spectrum of the Cu^{II} complex displays three bands at 659, 581 and 493 nm which may be assigned to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ and charge transfer transitions, respectively, proper for square planer geometry^{17,18}. The value of magnetic moment 1.84 B.M. consistent with one unpaired electron in square planer complex of Cu^{II} ion. The Ti^{III} complex shows only one broad band at 544 nm which is obviously derived from the transition ${}^2T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$, for an octahedral geometry around Ti^{III} ion. The broad band and double-hump nature of the spectrum attributed to the manifestation of the Jahn-Teller distortion in the complex¹⁹. The magnetic moment value of Ti^{III} complex was found to be 1.79 B.M. corresponds to one unpaired electron. The electronic spectrum of Cr^{III} complex shows three bands at 555, 412 and 246 nm assignable to ${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$, transitions, respectively, in an octahedral environment around Cr^{III}

ion²⁰. The reflectance spectral parameters for Cr^{III} complex are found to be $Dq = 1801 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $B' = 724 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\beta = 0.786$, $\nu_2/\nu_1 = 1.35$ and $\beta^\circ = 21.4$. The reduction of B value from the free ion suggests delocalization of electron on metal into molecular orbitals covering both the metal and the ligand. Also the lowering of β° value (21.4%) indicate the covalent nature of Cr^{III} complex. The magnetic moment of Cr^{III} complex is 3.92 B.M. suggests high-spin octahedral geometry for the Cr^{III} complex. The iron(III) complex displays three weak bands at 739, 560 and 437 nm which may be assigned to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g$, ${}^4A_{1g}(G)$, transitions, respectively for an octahedral geometry²¹. Fe^{III} complex shows magnetic moment 5.88 B.M. corresponds to five unpaired electrons. The Zr^{IV} and UO_2^{VI} complexes are found to be diamagnetic as expected from their f^0 electronic configuration and there is no either electronic d-d transition or significant magnetic moment.

Thermogravimetric analyses :

The thermal behaviors of the ligand and its complexes were characterized by thermogravimetric analysis in dynamic air with a heating rate of $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ within a temperature range $40\text{--}700 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. All the complexes show a gradual mass loss indicating decomposition by fragmentation with increase in temperature. Thermograms of Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Ti^{III} , Cr^{III} and Fe^{III} complexes indicate the loss of two equivalence of water between $140\text{--}230 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ indicating the presence of these water molecules as coordinated water one [% weight loss obs./calcd. : Mn^{II} : 8.38/7.26, Co^{II} : 8.32/7.20, Ni^{II} : 7.96/7.21, Ti^{III} : 4.22/3.55, Cr^{III} : 4.12/3.53 and Fe^{III} : 4.24/3.50]. The Cu^{II} , Zr^{IV} and UO_2^{VI} complexes are almost stable up to $250 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ indicating that absence of lattice or coordinated water molecule. After dehydration the organic part of the complexes may decompose in one or more steps with the possibility of the formation of one or two intermediates. These intermediates may include the metal ion with a part of the Schiff base and these intermediates may finally decompose to stable metal oxides. The initial decomposition and inflection temperatures have been used as an indication of the thermal stability of the complexes. The decomposition of all complexes ended with oxide formation. The metal content percentages of the complexes were calculated from the corresponding stoichiometric metal oxides formed in the final step and compared with those

obtained from the metal content as determined by microanalysis. The average metal percentages were found to be in good agreement with those calculated from the tentative formulae based on the elemental analysis. Horowitz and Metzger method was used to calculate various kinetic parameters²². The activation entropy S^* , the activation enthalpy H^* and the free energy of activation G^* were calculated using the following equations :

$$S^* = 2.303 (\log Ah/KT) R, H^* = E^* - RT \text{ and } G^* = H^* - T_s S^*$$

where K and h are the Boltzman's constants and Plank's constants respectively. The calculated values of these parameters for the decomposition are given in Table 3. The high value of activation energy for complexes as compared to ligand reflects the higher thermal stability of complexes. The entropy of activation was found to have negative values for all complexes, which indicates that the decomposition reactions proceed at a lower rate.

cal conductivity of the complexes have positive temperature coefficient i.e. with an increase in temperature, conductivity increases exponentially. The increase starts when charge carriers have enough activation energy. Also during the increases of temperature the mobility of these charge carriers increases. This is the property of typical semiconductor²⁴. The conductivity of the free ligand (H_2L) is increased on complexing with metal ions. This behavior is attributed to the inclusion of the various metal cations in the π -electron delocalization of the ligand. The electrical conductivity of the complexes lies in the range $4.46 \times 10^{-11} - 2.63 \times 10^{-06} \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The activation energy of electrical conduction of these complexes was found in the range 0.027–0.067 eV.

Antimicrobial activity :

The ligand and its complexes were screened for their antibacterial activity against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* strains. The antibacterial activity was evaluated by the Disc dif-

Table 3. Thermal decomposition data of ligand and its complexes

Sl. no.	Compd.	M.p.*/Half Decomp. temp. (°C)	Activation energy E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	Frequency factor Z (s ⁻¹)	Entropy change $-\Delta S$ (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	Free energy change ΔG (kJ mol ⁻¹)
1.	H ₂ L	308	11.35	20.42	271.6	28.06
2.	[MnL·2H ₂ O]	322	15.69	12.33	276.4	32.14
3.	[CoL·2H ₂ O]	418	53.13	60.56	261.9	71.23
4.	[NiL·2H ₂ O]	429	29.28	33.46	268.0	48.10
5.	[CuL]	366	39.87	40.63	265.1	56.81
6.	[TiL·Cl·H ₂ O]	425	48.51	62.61	26.17	66.78
7.	[CrL·Cl·H ₂ O]	409	40.42	49.04	263.9	58.43
8.	[FeL·Cl·H ₂ O]	420	38.40	41.84	265.7	56.81
9.	[Zr(OH) ₂ ·L]	422	57.36	52.90	263.3	75.61
10.	[UO ₂ ·L]	378	52.56	54.67	276.7	62.65

Electrical conductivity :

According to thermal decomposition temperatures the solid-state electrical conductivity of the complexes was measured in their compressed pellet form by two probe method over a wide range of temperature, i.e. from room temperature to 403 K. The electrical conductivity and the activation energy values of the complexes are given in Table 2. The electrical conductivity (σ) varies exponentially with the absolute temperature according to the relationship $\sigma = \sigma_0 \exp [-E_a/kT]$, where E_a is the thermal activation energy for the electrical conductivity and K is Boltzmann's constant²³. It was observed that the electri-

fusion method²⁵. The compounds were dissolved in dimethylsulfoxide at 500 and 1000 ppm concentration. The activity was measured by measuring the diameter of the zone of inhibition in millimeter. Minimum inhibitory concentrations of these compounds were determined by literature method²⁵. The results for antibacterial study are interpreted by measuring the zones of inhibition of growth of the bacterial culture. The results show that ligand and all complexes exhibit bacteriostatic behavior towards the bacterial strains. All the compounds were found to be show almost low to moderate bacteriocidal nature against the bacterial strains. Cu^{II} and Cr^{III} complexes were found

to show good activity against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* respectively. In general the results reveal that, the activity of the ligand was found to be enhanced on complexation with metal ions. It has been observed that the metal complexes show enhanced antibacterial activity as compared to the free ligand against the same organism under identical experimental conditions. This is because of the chelation. According to Tweedy's chelation theory²⁷, the chelation reduces the polarity of the metal atom mainly because of the partial sharing of its positive charge with donor groups and possible π electron delocalisation over the whole ring^{28,29}. This increases the lipophilic character of the metal chelate which favours its permeating through the lipid layer of bacterial membranes. The toxicity increases with increase in concentration of the complexes. This is because of the chelation, which reduces the polarity of metal ion due to partial sharing of its positive charge with donor groups and also due to the delocalisation of π electrons over the whole chelate ring. Thus chelation increases lipophilic character in the complexes and results in enhancement of activity.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AR grade obtained from the commercial source. $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{MnCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, FeCl_3 and $\text{CrCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, TiCl_3 (anhydrous), uranyl nitrate hexahydrate, zirconyl acetate and dehydroacetic acid were procured from SD's fine chemicals and used as such. Thiocarbohydrazide was prepared by the known method.

Synthesis of ligand (H_2L): A solution of thiocarbohydrazide (1.06 g, 0.01 mol) in 25 ml hot DMF was added to a dehydroacetic acid (3.36 g, 0.02 mol) dissolved in ethanol (25 ml) with stirring. The reaction mixture was heated under reflux on a sand bath for 4 h. After reducing the solvent volume to ca. 30 mL and cooling to room temperature, the yellow colored solid obtained was filtered, washed with methanol and dried in desiccators over silica gel. Yield 70%, m.p. 286 °C; $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 13.34 (2H, br, phenolic), 8.09 (2NH, s, imino), 5.73 (2H, s, ring-H), 2.86 (6H, s, CH_3 ring), 2.15 (6H, s, CH_3 , imine).

Synthesis of complexes: Equimolar quantities (0.01 mol) of Schiff base and appropriate metal salt were dissolved separately in DMF (25 ml) and ethanol respec-

N',N''-Bis[(1*E*)-1-(4-hydroxy-6-methyl-2-oxo-2*H*-pyran-3-yl)ethylidene]thiocarbohydrazide

tively and mixed in hot condition under continuous stirring. The resulting mixture was refluxed for 4–5 h. On cooling to room temperature, the colored complexes precipitated out was filtered, washed with hot water, alcohol, DMF and petroleum ether and finally dried under vacuum at room temperature. Yield 65–70%.

Physical measurements:

Elemental analysis carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were obtained using Carlo Erba 1108 analyser in micro analytical laboratory, CDRI, Lucknow. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 597 spectrophotometer using KBr pallets at SAIF, Punjab University, Chandigarh. $^1\text{H NMR}$ spectra of ligand were obtained using a Bruker Auance-II 400 NMR spectrophotometer in DMSO solvent at SAIF, Punjab University, Chandigarh. The electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded on Varian SE UV-NIR spectrophotometer at RSIC, IIT, Chennai using MgO as reference. Magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature by Gouy's method using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as a calibrant and the diamagnetic corrections were made using Pascal's constants. The solid state d.c. electrical conductivity of compounds was measured by Zentech Electrometer in their compressed pellet form over 313–403 K temperature range. TG analysis of the complexes was carried out on Perkin-Elmer TG-2 thermobalance in ambient air with a heating rate of 10 °C per min. Metal contents of the complexes were analysed gravimetrically after decomposing the complexes with a mixture of HClO_4 , H_2SO_4 and HNO_3 and then igniting to metal oxide.

Antimicrobial activity:

Antibacterial activity of the ligand and the complexes was carried out against the bacteria *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* by agar diffusion method²⁹. DMSO was taken as control. In order to check the potency of compounds, the solutions were prepared with 500 and 1000 ppm concentration in DMSO. The solutions pre-

pared were soaked in Whatmann filter paper No. 1 paper disc having diameter of 10 mm. These discs were kept on the previously seeded petri plates for incubation at 37 °C for 24 h. The diameters of the zones of inhibition were measured in millimeter.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Director, SAIF, Lucknow for providing ¹H NMR, IR, elemental analysis facilities and Director, SAIF, Chennai for recording electronic spectra.

References

1. M. R. Maurya, M. Bisht, A. Kumar, M. L. Kuzenetsov, F. Avecilla and J. C. Pessoa, *Dalton Trans.*, 2011, **40**, 6968.
2. S. Kumar, D. N. Dhar and P. N. Saxena, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 2009, **68**, 181.
3. G. G. Mohamed, M. M. Omar and M. M. Hindy, *Turk. J. Chem.*, 2006, **30**, 361.
4. Y. Shibuya, K. Nabari, M. Kondo, S. Yasue, K. Maeda, F. Uchida and H. Kawaguchi, *Chem. Lett.*, 2008, **37**, 78.
5. A. Malik, S. Sher Khan, R. Wajid, H. Zonera, R. Abdur and I. Muhammad, *African J. Biotech.*, 2011, **10**, 209.
6. J. Li, B. Xu, W. Jiang, B. Zhou, W. Zeng and S. Qin, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 2008, **33**, 975.
7. A. S. Munde, A. N. Jagdale, S. N. Jadhav and T. K. Chondhekar, *J. Serb. Chem. Soc.*, 2010, **75**, 349.
8. V. B. Badwaik and A. S. Aswar, *Russ. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 2010, **41**, 1611.
9. R. Chandra, *Acta Chim. Hung.*, 1991, **73**, 128.
10. M. R. Maurya, A. K. Chandrakar and S. Chand, *J. Mol. Catal. A : Gen.*, 2007, **270**, 225.
11. K. Natarajan, S. Karvembu, S. Hemlatha and R. Prabhakaran, *Inorg. Chem. Commun.*, 2003, **6**, 486.
12. V. V. Dhande, V. B. Badwaik and A. S. Aswar, *Russ. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 2007, **52**, 1206.
13. A. P. Mishra and M. Khare, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **77**, 367.
14. B. N. Patel, P. S. Patel and B. P. Patel, *Inter. J. Chem. Tech. Res.*, 2011, **3**, 565.
15. N. H. Patel, H. M. Parekh and M. N. Patel, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 2005, **30**, 13.
16. M. G. Drebe, V. J. T. Raju and N. Retta, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Ethiop.*, 2002, **16**, 53.
17. B. N. Figgis, "Introduction to Ligand Fields", Interscience Publication, New York, 1967, 316.
18. A. Syamal and K. J. Kale, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1978, **16**, 46.
19. A. S. Aswar, A. D. Bansod, S. R. Aswale and P. R. Mandlik, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2004, **43**, 1892.
20. B. T. Thaker, A. Patel, J. Lekhadia and P. Thaker, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2000, **39**, 1070.
21. S. D. Dhumwad, K. B. Gudasi and T. R. Goudar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1994, **38**, 320.
22. H. H. Horowitz and G. Metzger, *J. Anal. Chem.*, 1963, **35**, 1464.
23. A. P. Mishra and L. R. Pandey, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2005, **44**, 94.
24. M. Koca, F. Dagdelen and Y. Aydogdu, *Mater. Lett.*, 2004, **58**, 2901.
25. N. Raman, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **86**, 1143.
26. R. Maruvada, S. C. Pal and G. B. Nair, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1994, **20**, 115.
27. D. Thangadurai and K. Natarajan, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 2001, **30**, 569.
28. A. P. Mishra and M. Soni, *Metal Based Drugs*, 2008, **7**, 256.
29. P. K. Mukharjee, K. Shah, S. N. Giri, M. Pal and B. P. Shah, *Ind. J. Microbio.*, 1995, **35**, 327.

